

A Comparative Clinical Evaluation of Soft Tissue Changes Following Two Different Incision Techniques in Second Stage Implant Surgery

Dr. Anita Panchal¹, Dr. Paridha Godiawala², Dr. Bhoomi Shah³, Dr. Priyal Thakkar⁴, Dr. Neh Shukla⁵,
Dr. Kalpesh Vaishnav⁶

¹Professor and Head of Department, Department of Periodontology and Implantology, College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Manipur, Bopal, Ahmedabad, India

^{2,4,5}Post Graduate Student, Department of Periodontology and Implantology, College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Manipur, Bopal, Ahmedabad, India

³M.D.S., Department of Periodontology and Implantology, College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Manipur, Bopal, Ahmedabad, India

⁶Professor and Head of Department, Department of Prosthodontics and Crown and Bridge, Karnavati School of Dentistry, Gandhinagar, India

Received: Apr 04, 2026

Accepted: Apr 28, 2026

Published: May 01, 2026

Abstract— Dental implants are a predictable treatment for replacing missing teeth, with success relying on osseointegration and stable peri-implant soft tissue. Esthetic outcomes, especially papilla preservation, are critical in the anterior region, as inadequate papilla can create “black triangles.” Papilla formation depends on vertical (bone crest to contact point) and horizontal (inter-implant/tooth distance) dimensions, tissue biotype, and surgical technique. Various incision designs, including mid-crestal and I-shaped, have been proposed to optimize soft tissue healing during second-stage implant surgery.

Aim: To compare soft tissue changes and papilla formation around implants following mid-crestal versus I-shaped incision techniques.

Materials and Methods: 60 implant sites in 30 patients (11 males, 19 females; 25–65 years) were randomized into Group 1 (mid-crestal incision) and Group 2 (I-shaped incision). Clinical parameters—modified Plaque Index (mPI), modified Gingival Index (mGI), Papillary Index Score (PIS), and measurements of vertical (D1), horizontal (D2), and papilla height (D3)—were recorded at baseline, 90, and 180 days. Statistical analysis used ANOVA, unpaired t-test, and Z-test ($p < 0.05$).

Results: Both groups showed significant improvement in mPI, mGI, and D1/D3 over time. Group 2 demonstrated superior papilla fill, with 53.3% achieving complete fill (PIS 3) at 180 days, compared to none in Group 1. Papilla presence correlated with D1 and D2.

Conclusion: The I-shaped incision preserves vascularity and promotes better papilla formation and esthetic outcomes than the mid-crestal technique

Keywords— Dental implants, Papilla, I-shaped incision, Mid-crestal incision, Soft tissue management

I. INTRODUCTION

Dental implants have become a routine treatment for replacing missing teeth, supported by the biologic process of osseointegration, where titanium bonds with bone. [1] This principle has proven successful in complete edentulism and extended to single-tooth cases with stable survival rates and marginal bone preservation. [2]

Esthetics, particularly soft tissue management, are now critical for implant success, especially in the anterior maxilla where deficiencies in peri-implant papilla can create cosmetic issues such as “black triangles”. Loss of alveolar bone and ridge dimension after extraction or infection further complicates papilla regeneration. Factors influencing papilla presence include bone quality, implant positioning, mucosal characteristics, and angulation between adjacent implants. [3]

Secondary contributors to peri-implant bone loss include surgical stress, implant design, and microgaps at the abutment interface. Various surgical techniques scalpel, punch, diode laser, U-shaped, and I-shaped

incisions have been explored to preserve or regenerate papilla during second-stage surgery. Despite advances, predictable papilla regeneration remains a complex challenge, underscoring the importance of surgical design and peri-implant tissue management. [4] The present study is to evaluate the incidence of papilla with respect to soft tissue changes around implants following two different incision techniques in the second stage of implant surgery.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

This is a type of randomized controlled trial carried out in participants reporting to outpatient department of Periodontology, College of Dental Sciences and Research Centre, Manipur, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India for which approval was taken from the institutional ethical committee.

All the patients were informed about the study and written consent was obtained. A total of 30 patients (11 males and 19 females) of age group 25-65 years with good systemic health and edentulous areas in either arch with implants placed three months prior to the second stage surgery, and showed satisfactory healing with no periodontal disease, with suitable soft and hard tissue without requiring augmentation, a thick gingival biotype, good compliance with follow-up and oral hygiene maintenance, and a stable socio-economic background were included. Whereas patients with any uncontrolled active systemic disease, implant sites with acute infection, pregnant or lactating women, patients with deleterious habits such as smoking or tobacco consumption, those with poor oral hygiene or poor periodontal conditions, patients with a thin gingival biotype, patients who required to undergo the guided bone regeneration (GBR) procedure, patients on medications that act on bone remodelling (e.g. bisphosphonates) or interfere with gingival condition (e.g. calcium channel blockers), patients with history of radiotherapy or chemotherapy were excluded.

All the selected patients received full-mouth Scaling and Root Planing (SRP). Following SRP, a pre-operative radiograph of the arch consisting of the edentulous area was taken using a cone beam computed tomography (CBCT). After this, upper and lower alginate impressions of these patients were recorded and cast models were prepared. Post preliminary preparation, implants were placed on 60 sites of 30 patients. After 3 months of the implant placement, the patients were recalled for an intraoral peri-apical radiograph to check for the successful osseointegration.

Based on incision type for second stage surgery, patients were randomly divided into two groups:

Group I: Mid-crestal incision

Group II: I-shaped incision

After surgery the cover screw was replaced by the healing abutment in all patients and the surgical site was further closed by surgical sutures. Routine post-operative instructions were given to the patients and they were then recalled on 7th day for suture removal.

Later the patients were recalled when the prosthesis was ready for delivery. The date of prosthesis delivery was considered to be the baseline. At baseline, all the parameters like Modified Plaque Index (mPI) given by Mombelli et al. (1987) [5], Modified Gingival Index (mGI) given by Mombelli et al. (1987) [5], Papillary index score (PIS) given by Jemt (1997) [2], Distance from base of contact point to bone crest (D1), Inter-implant to tooth distance (D2), Distance from base of contact point to tip of papilla (D3) were recorded.

For recording D1, a plastic probe was used after administration of the local anaesthetic agent. For recording D2, a radiographic analysis was performed using a grid, standardized in the ratio of 1:1, using the parallelism technique through positioners for peri-apical radiographs to control the projection geometry. For recording of D3, a periodontal probe was used and the PIS was recorded visually. The patient was recalled on 90th day after prosthesis delivery and all the parameters except D2 were recorded again. Similarly, on the 180th day from baseline, all parameters except D2 were recorded again. D2 was only recorded at the baseline. The collected data was put to statistical analysis.

A. GROUP 1- MID-CRESTAL INCISION FOR IMPLANT PLACEMENT IN 15

Fig. 1 Mid-crestal incision

Fig. 2 D1 = 5.8 mm at baseline

Fig. 3 D1 = 6 mm at 180 days from baseline

Fig. 4 D2 = 5 mm at baseline

Fig. 5 PIS = 0 at baseline

Fig. 6 PIS = 0 at 180 days from baseline

GROUP 2- I-SHAPED INCISION FOR IMPLANT PLACEMENT IN 16

Fig. 7 I – shaped incision

Fig. 8 D1= 6 mm at baseline

Fig. 9 D1= 6.2 mm at 180 days from baseline

Fig. 10 D2= 3 mm at baseline

Fig. 11 D3 = 1.5 mm at baseline

Fig. 12 D3 = 1 mm at 180 days from baseline

Fig. 13 PIS=0 at baseline

Fig. 14 PIS=1 at 90 days from baseline

Fig. 15 PIS=3 at 180 days from baseline

III. RESULT

The study data were analyzed using SPSS version 22, with results expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Intragroup comparisons across baseline, 90 days, and 180 days were assessed using one-way ANOVA, while intergroup differences were tested with the unpaired t-test. The Z-test was applied to evaluate the

relationship between inter-implant to tooth distance and papilla incidence. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$, with $p < 0.01$ considered highly significant and $p > 0.05$ non-significant. The study maintained 80% power ($\alpha = 5\%$, $\beta = 20\%$). Group 1 included patients treated with a mid-crestal incision, and Group 2 comprised those treated with an I-shaped incision.

TABLE 1
DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Study Design	Total no. of cases	Sex		Age range (in years)	Total no. of Groups	
Randomized Clinical Trial	30 (30 sites)	M 11	F 19	25-65 Years	Group 1 15 Patients (15 sites)	Group 2 15 Patients (15 sites)

The Demographic Data of the Study i.e., Statistical Data of Males and Females Included in the Study.

TABLE 2
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF MODIFIED PLAQUE INDEX (mPI) SCORES

Group	Baseline	90 Days	180 Days	F	p - Value
Group I	2.85 + 0.25	2.36 + 0.3	1.97 + 0.37	59.37	<0.00001**
Group II	2.41 + 0.41	1.99 + 0.4	1.75 + 0.42	24.42	<0.00001**

(One - Way ANOVA Test)

Intragroup Comparison of Modified Plaque Index (Mpi) Scores that Showed Highly Statistically Significant Difference in Group 1 and Group 2 at Baseline, 90 Days and 180 Days.

TABLE 3
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF MODIFIED PLAQUE INDEX (mPI) SCORES

	Group I	Group II	p - Value
Baseline	2.85 + 0.25	2.41 + 0.41	0.00*
90 Days	2.36 + 0.3	1.99 + 0.4	0.01*
180 Days	1.97 + 0.37	1.75 + 0.42	0.14

**Comparison of Group 1 with Group 2 Baseline with its respective 90 days and 180 days time interval

(Unpaired t-test)

Intergroup comparison of Modified Plaque Index (mPI) Scores that showed statistically significant difference between Group 1 and Group 2 from baseline to 90 days and statistically non-significant difference from baseline to 180 days.

TABLE 4
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF MODIFIED GINGIVAL INDEX (mGI) SCORES

Group	Baseline	90 Days	180 Days	F	p - Value
Group I	2.15 + 0.82	1.21 + 0.87	0.65 + 0.48	17.23	<0.00001**
Group II	2.32 + 0.65	0.79 + 0.63	0.64 + 0.55	26.94	<0.00001**

**Comparison Of Group 1 And Group 2 Baseline with its Respective 90 Days and 180 Days Time Interval (One - Way ANOVA Test)

Intragroup comparison of Modified Gingival Index (mGI) Scores that showed highly statistically significant difference in Group 1 and Group 2 at baseline, 90 days and 180 days.

TABLE 5
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF MODIFIED GINGIVAL INDEX (mGI) SCORES

	Group I	Group II	p - Value
Baseline	2.15 ± 0.82	2.32 ± 0.65	0.54
90 Days	1.21 ± 0.87	0.79 ± 0.63	0.14
180 Days	0.65 ± 0.48	0.64 ± 0.55	0.97

**Comparison of Group 1 with Group 2 Baseline with its respective 90 days and 180 days time interval (Unpaired t-test)

Intergroup comparison of Modified Gingival Index (mGI) Scores that showed statistically non-significant difference between Group 1 and Group 2 from baseline to 90 days and from baseline to 180 days.

TABLE 6
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF DISTANCE FROM BONE CREST TO CONTACT POINT (D1)

Groups	Baseline		90 days		180 days		F	p - Value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Group I	6.03	0.83	6.29	0.79	6.75	0.80	113.19	<0.00001**
Group II	5.83	0.41	6.13	0.40	6.33	0.45	64.95	<0.00001**

**Comparison of Group 1 and Group 2 Baseline with its respective 90 days and 180 days time interval (One-way ANOVA test)

Intragroup comparison of distance from bone crest to contact point (D1) that showed highly statistically significant difference in Group 1 and Group 2 at baseline, 90 days and 180 days.

TABLE 7
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF DISTANCE FROM BONE CREST TO CONTACT POINT (D1)

	Group I	Group II	p - Value
Baseline	6.03 ± 0.83	5.83 ± 0.41	0.41
90 days	6.29 ± 0.79	6.13 ± 0.40	0.49
180 days	6.75 ± 0.80	6.33 ± 0.45	0.09

Comparison of Group 1 with Group 2 Baseline, 90 Days and 180 Days Time Interval (Unpaired T-Test)

Intergroup comparison of distance from bone crest to contact point (D1) that showed no statistically significant difference between Group 1 and Group 2 from baseline to 90 days and from baseline to 180 days.

TABLE 8
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF DISTANCE FROM CONTACT POINT TO TIP OF PAPILLA (D3)

Groups	Baseline		90 days		180 days		F	p - Value
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Group I	2.33	0.66	2.49	0.65	2.64	0.68	12.15	<0.00001**
Group II	2.8	0.37	3.05	0.35	3.21	0.38	56.2	<0.00001**

**Comparison of Group 1 and Group 2 Baseline with its respective 90 days and 180 days time interval (One-way ANOVA repeated measures test)

Intragroup comparison of distance from contact point to tip of papilla (D3) that showed highly statistically significant difference in Group 1 and Group 2 at baseline, 90 days and 180 days.

TABLE 9
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF DISTANCE FROM CONTACT POINT TO TIP OF PAPILLA (D3)

	Group I	Group II	p - Value
Baseline	2.33 ± 0.66	2.8 ± 0.37	0.02*
90 days	2.49 ± 0.65	3.05 ± 0.35	0.008*
180 days	2.64 ± 0.68	3.21 ± 0.38	0.009*

* Comparison of group 1 with group 2 baseline, 90 days and 180 days time interval (Unpaired t-test)

Intergroup comparison of distance from contact point to tip of papilla (D3) that showed statistically significant difference between Group 1 and Group 2 from baseline to 90 days and from baseline to 180 days.

TABLE 10
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF DISTANCE BETWEEN INTER-IMPLANT- TOOTH (D2)

D2 (mm)	GROUP 1			GROUP 2		
	No. of sites	Presence of papilla (%)	P value	No. of sites	Presence of papilla (%)	P value
2-2.5	5	33	0.000**	3	20	0.000**
3-3.5	9	60	0.002*	9	60	0.002*
4-4.5	1	6.70	0.000**	3	20	0.000**

**Comparison of Group 1 and Group 2 in relation to the incidence of papilla with respect to the inter-implant – tooth distance (D2) (z- test)

Intragroup comparison of distance between inter-implant and tooth that showed highly statistically significant difference when D2 is 2-2.5 and 4-4.5 mm in Group 1 and Group 2 while statistically significant result when D2 is 3-3.5 in Group 1 and Group 2.

TABLE 11
INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF DISTANCE BETWEEN INTER-IMPLANT- TOOTH (D2)

D2 (mm)	GROUP 1		GROUP 2		P value
	No. of sites	Presence of papilla (%)	No. of sites	Presence of papilla (%)	
2-2.5	5	33	3	20	0.37
3-3.5	9	60	9	60	1
4-4.5	1	6.70	3	20	0.04*

**Comparison of Group 1 with Group 2 in relation to the incidence of papilla with respect to the inter-implant – tooth distance (D2) (z-test)

Intergroup comparison of distance between inter-implant and tooth that showed statistically non significant difference when D2 is 2-2.5 and 3-3.5 mm in Group 1 and Group 2 while statistically significant result when D2 is 4-4.5 mm in Group 1 and Group 2.

TABLE 12
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF DISTANCE FROM BONE CREST TO CONTACT POINT TO TIP OF PAPILLA (D1-D3) FOR GROUP 1

	D1	D3	p – Value
Baseline	6.03 ± 0.83	2.33 ± 0.66	<0.00001**
90 days	6.29 ± 0.79	2.49 ± 0.65	<0.00001**
180 days	6.75 ± 0.80	2.64 ± 0.68	<0.00001**

**Comparison of Group 1 Baseline with its respective 90 days and 180 days time interval (Unpaired t-Test)

The above table shows:

Intragroup comparison of distance from bone crest to contact point to tip of papilla i.e D1 to D3 that showed highly statistically significant difference in Group 1 at baseline, 90 days and 180 days.

TABLE 13
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF DISTANCE FROM BONE CREST TO CONTACT POINT TO TIP OF PAPILLA (D1-D3) FOR GROUP 2

	D1	D3	p – Value
Baseline	5.83 ± 0.41	2.8 ± 0.37	<0.00001**
90 days	6.13 ± 0.40	3.05 ± 0.35	<0.00001**
180 days	6.33 ± 0.45	3.21 ± 0.38	<0.00001**

**Comparison of Group 2 Baseline with its respective 90 days and 180 days time interval (Unpaired t-Test)

Intragroup comparison of distance from bone crest to contact point to tip of papilla i.e D1 to D3 that showed highly statistically significant difference in Group 2 at baseline, 90 days and 180 days.

TABLE 14
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF PAPILLA INDEX SCORE (PIS) FOR GROUP 1

SCORE	Baseline		90 Days		180 Days	
	Number	(%)	Number	(%)	Number	(%)
0	11	73.3	04	26.7	01	7
1	04	26.7	11	73.3	11	73
2	0	0	0	0	03	20
3	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	15	100%	15	100%	15	100%

Comparison of Group 1 Baseline with its respective 90 days and 180 days time interval

Intragroup comparison of the Papillary Index Score (PIS) that showed the incidence of the presence of papilla in Group 1 at baseline, 90 days and 180 days.

TABLE 15
INTRAGROUP COMPARISON OF PAPILLA INDEX SCORE (PIS) FOR GROUP 2

SCORE	Baseline		90 Days		180 Days	
	Number	(%)	Number	(%)	Number	(%)
0	12	80	01	6.7	01	6.7
1	03	20	02	13.3	02	13.3
2	0	0	11	73.3	04	26.7
3	0	0	01	6.7	08	53.3
4	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	15	100%	15	100%	15	100%

Comparison of Group 2 Baseline with its respective 90 days and 180 days time interval .

Intragroup comparison of the Papillary Index Score (PIS) that showed the incidence of the presence of papilla in Group 2 at baseline, 90 days and 180 days.

IV. DISCUSSION

The study showed a significant reduction in mPI and mGI scores in both groups over time. Group 1 mPI decreased from 2.85±0.25 to 1.97±0.37, while Group 2 decreased from 2.41±0.41 to 1.75±0.42, (Table 2 & 3) with significant intragroup changes and limited intergroup differences. Similarly, mGI scores reduced from 2.15±0.82 to 0.65±0.48 in Group 1 and from 2.32±0.65 to 0.64±0.55 (Table 4 & 5) in Group 2, showing highly significant intragroup but non-significant intergroup differences. Slightly higher scores in Group 1 may be due to sutures causing plaque accumulation. These findings align with Kamakshi et al. (2021) [7], who reported greater reduction with I-shaped incision (0.44) and diode laser (0.11) compared to conventional technique.

The mean distance from bone crest to contact point (D1) in Group 1 increased from 6.03±0.83 at baseline to 6.29±0.79 at 90 days and 6.75±0.80 at 180 days, while in Group 2 it increased from 5.83±0.40 to 6.13±0.40 and 6.33±0.45, (Table 6) respectively. Both groups showed highly significant intragroup changes over time; however, intergroup comparison revealed no statistically significant difference between baseline, 90 days, and 180 days, even with D1 values between 5–7 mm or with increased distance due to bone resorption. (Table 7)

These findings are consistent with Romeo et al. (2008) [8], who reported that a vertical distance <7 mm between contact point and bone is associated with papilla presence. However, they contrast with Grunder (2000)⁹, who observed successful papilla regeneration even at distances up to 9 mm.

The mean distance from contact point to tip of papilla (D3) in Group 1 increased from 2.33±0.66 at baseline to 2.49±0.65 at 90 days and 2.64±0.68 at 180 days, while in Group 2 it increased from 2.80±0.37 to

3.05±0.35 and 3.21±0.38, respectively. **(Table 8)** Both groups showed highly significant intragroup differences, and intergroup comparison was also statistically significant. **(Table 9)**

These findings are in agreement with Romeo et al. (2008) [8], who reported significant papilla presence when CPB ≤7 mm (71.8% for <5 mm and 70.4% for 5–7 mm). The results are partially consistent with Choquet et al. (2001) [10] and Gastaldo et al. (2004) [11], who found predictable papilla regeneration at <5 mm and reduced predictability beyond 5 mm.

The intragroup comparison of implant-tooth distance (D2) showed highly significant differences in both groups. In Group 1, papilla presence was 33% at 2–2.5 mm, 60% at 3–3.5 mm, and 6.7% at 4–4.5 mm, while in Group 2 it was 20%, 60%, and 20%, respectively. A statistically significant difference was observed at 3–3.5 mm (60% in both groups). **(Table 10)** Intergroup comparison showed significance only at 4–4.5 mm, while it was non-significant at 2–2.5 mm and 3–3.5 mm. Higher papilla presence in Group 2 at 4–4.5 mm (by 13.3%) may be due to the papilla-sparing I-shaped incision. **(Table 11)**

These findings are consistent with Gastaldo et al. (2004) [11], who reported higher papilla incidence at 3–4 mm, and Romeo et al. (2008) [8], who found significant papilla presence at 2.5–4 mm. However, they contrast with Ryser et al. (2005) [12], who found no significant relationship between horizontal distance and papilla maintenance.

The comparison of D1–D3 showed that in Group 1, D3 was 2.64±0.68 when D1 was 6.75±0.80 at 180 days, while in Group 2, D3 was higher at 3.21±0.38 when D1 was 6.33±0.45. A highly significant difference was observed, indicating that as D1 increased (due to bone resorption), D3 also increased. However, greater papillary fill in Group 2 suggests better outcomes with the I-shaped incision compared to the conventional technique. **(Table 12 & 13)**

These findings are partially consistent with Gastaldo et al. (2004) [11], who reported higher papilla presence when D1 was 3–5 mm, and Choquet et al. (2001) [10], who found predictable papilla regeneration at ≤5 mm, with reduced predictability beyond 5 mm and limited influence of surgical technique when bone crest levels are optimal.

The Papillary Index Score (PIS) showed improvement over time in both groups. In Group 1, at baseline PIS 0 and 1 were seen in 73.3% and 26.7% cases, while at 180 days PIS 1 and 2 were observed in 73% and 20% cases, with no complete papilla fill (PIS 3). In Group 2, baseline values were 80% (PIS 0) and 20% (PIS 1), improving to 53.3% cases with complete papilla fill (PIS 3) and 26.7% with PIS 2 at 180 days. No PIS 4 was observed in either group. **(Table 14 & 15)**

These findings indicate superior papilla fill in Group 2 using the I-shaped incision, with 53.3% complete fill and 80% cases showing ≥50% papilla fill, whereas Group 1 showed no complete fill. The results are consistent with Kamakshi et al. (2021) [7], who reported improved papilla fill with modified incision techniques, and partially agree with Choquet et al. (2001) [10], who found papilla presence dependent mainly on bone crest distance with limited influence of surgical technique.

V. CONCLUSION

This randomized clinical trial included 60 implant sites (11 males, 19 females; 25–65 years) divided into Group 1 (mid-crestal incision) and Group 2 (I-shaped incision). Clinical parameters (mPI, mGI, PIS, D1, D2, D3) were recorded at baseline, 90, and 180 days. Both groups showed significant intragroup improvements, with Group 2 achieving superior papilla fill (53.3% complete at 180 days) compared to Group 1. Intergroup differences were limited, with significance noted for mPI (up to 90 days), D2 (3–3.5 mm), and D3 (90 and 180 days). Overall, papilla formation depends on vertical (D1) and horizontal (D2) distances, and the I-shaped incision preserves vascularity, allowing better papillary fill and more esthetic implant outcomes.

REFERENCES

- [1] Albrektsson T, Dahl E, Enbom L, Engevall S, Engquist B, Eriksson AR, Osseointegrated oral implants: a Swedish multicenter study of 8139 consecutively inserted Nobelpharma implants. *J Periodontol* 1988; 59:287-9.
- [2] Jemt T, Lekholm U. Osseointegrated implants in the treatment of partially edentulous patients: a pre-liminary study on 876 consecutively placed fixtures. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants* 1989; 4:211-7.
- [3] Israelson H, Plemons JM. Dental implants, regenerative techniques and periodontal plastic surgery to restore maxillary anterior aesthetics. *Int J Oral maxillofac implants* 1993; 8:555-61.
- [4] Eun-Kwon Lee et al. I-shaped incisions for papilla reconstruction in second stage implant surgery. *J Periodontal Implant Sci* 2010; 40:139-43.
- [5] Mombelli A, Van Oosten MAC, Schiirch E, Lang NP. The microbiota associated with successful or failing osseointegrated titanium implants. *Oral Microbiol Immunol* 1987; 2:145-51.
- [6] T Jemt. Regeneration of gingival papillae after single-implant treatment. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent.* 1997 Aug; 17(4):326-33.
- [7] L. N. V. Alekhya Kamakshi. Evaluation of papilla levels following three different techniques for the second stage of implants – A clinical and radiographic study. *J Indian Soc Periodontol.*2021; 25(3):270.
- [8] Romeo E, Lops D, Rossi A, Storelli S, Rozza R, Chiapasco M. Surgical and prosthetic management of interproximal region with single-implant restorations: 1-year prospective study. *J Periodontol.* 2008; 79:1048–55.
- [9] Grunder U. Stability of the mucosa; topography around single-tooth implants and adjacent teeth: 1-year results. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent* 2000; 20:11-17.
- [10] Choquet V, Hermans et al. Clinical and radiographic evaluation of the papilla level adjacent to single – tooth dental implants. A retrospective study in the maxillary anterior region. *J Periodontol* 2001; 72:1364-71.
- [11] Gastaldo J.F., Patricia Ramos Cury. Effect of the vertical and horizontal distances between adjacent implants and between a tooth and an implant on the incidence of interproximal papilla. *J Periodontol* 2004 Sep; 75(9):1242-6.
- [12] Ryser MR. et al. Correlation of papilla to crestal bone levels around single tooth implants in immediate or delayed crown protocols. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 2005; 63:1184-95.